

1. Main Principle

The database is built around: Technology Lineage, not organizations or publications.

Main Question:

How did the original Soviet HCFR concept evolve, and which of its elements were confirmed by each subsequent developer?

2. Database Architecture

HCFR_CONCEPT_LINEAGE

3. Root structure of technologies

HCFR_ROOT_001


```
|  └─ Lightbridge-LWR
|  └─ Lightbridge-SMR
|
└─ CHINA_HCF_001
```

4. Entities

PEOPLE

The idea behind creating a registry:

authors;

developers;

project managers.

TECHNOLOGY_CLAIMS

Every technical statement must have:

a source;

a status of credibility.

HCFR_FEATURES

Technology Feature Directory:

Code Feature

F001 Helical Twist

F002 Cruciform Geometry

F003 Self-Spacing

F004 Increased Surface Area

F005 Reduced Fuel Temperature

F006 Improved CHF Margin

F007 Metallic Fuel

F008 Dispersion Fuel

F009 Burnable Poison Integration

5. Contents

Patents

History of the Concept

Who first proposed HCFR;

At what institute;

In what year.

6. Changes

The Change Log section is used to track changes to the database structure, not its data. A change in the architecture requires a new first version number. A change in the root structure requires a new second version number. Version numbers are defined only in the file name; the change date is not indicated.

Developers2

Developer_ID	Organization	Country	Type	Website	Notes
KI_RIAR	Kurchatov Institute /	Russia	Research Institute	https://www.pnpi.nrcki.ru/ustanovki/	Historic HCF development
MIT	Massachusetts Instit	USA	University	https://www.mit.edu/	HCF research
LIGHTBRIDGE	Lightbridge Corporat	USA	Commercial Company	https://www.ltbridge.com/	Commercial metallic HCF fuel
INL	Idaho National Labor	USA	National Laboratory	https://inl.gov/	Fuel testing and analysis
CIAE	China Institute of Atc	China	Research Institute	https://www.ciae.ac.cn/zh401en/inde	Chinese HCF-related research
CGN	China General Nuclea	China	Utility	https://en.cgnpc.com.cn/	Advanced fuel development
Research					
Research					
XJTU					
NUAA					
CEA / Framatome					

Publications3

Publication_ID	Title	Authors	Year	Organization	Country	Concept_ID	Document_Type	Link	Notes
PUB-USSR-001	Historical S	Various	1980	Kurchatov Institu	USSR/Russia	USSR HCF	Historical Reference		Placeholder record for expansion
PUB-MIT-001	MIT crucifc	MIT Resear	2000	MIT	USA	MIT HCF	Research Paper		Placeholder record for expansion
PUB-LB-001	Lightbridge	Lightbridge	2015	Lightbridge	USA	Lightbridge Fue	Corporate Technical Paper		Placeholder record for expansion

Reactors5

Reactor_ID	Reactor_Name	Country	Reactor_Type	Operator	Concept_ID	Status	Notes
1							

Irradiation6

Campaign_ID	Reactor_ID	Concept_ID	Start_Year	End_Year	Burnup	Results	Reference_ID
1							

PIE7

PIE_ID	Concept_ID	Reactor_ID	Year	Findings	Reference_ID
1					

Manufacturing8

Manufacturing_ID	Concept_ID	Fuel_Fabrication	Cladding_Fabrication	Assembly_Fabrication	Supplier	Notes
1						

Licensing9

License_ID	Concept_ID	Country	Regulator	Status	Year	Notes
1						

References10

Reference_ID	Reference_ID2	Reference_ID3	Reference_ID4	Reference_ID5	Reference_ID6
REF-USSR-001	Initial Soviet HCF evidence	1980	Historical Source		USSR HCF
REF-MIT-001	Initial MIT HCF evidence co	2000	Publication		MIT HCF
REF-LB-001	Initial Lightbridge evidence	2015	Publication		Lightbridge Fuel

TRL11

TRL	TRL_Content
TRL 1 — Fundamentals	Formulating the concept and publishing initial research
TRL 2 — Technology Concept	Generating the idea, identifying potential applications
TRL 3 — Experimental Validation	Initial analytical and lab studies to validate the concept
TRL 4 — Component Verification (in the lab)	Integrating the basic parts under lab conditions
TRL 5 — Prototype (in a Real-World Environment)	Building a mock-up and testing it under conditions that simulate field use
TRL 6 — Model or Prototype (in the Real-World Environment)	Testing the technology under conditions as close as possible to actual field use
TRL 7 — Prototype Demonstration	Running the technology under actual field conditions, evaluating its performance, and troubleshooting
TRL 8 — Complete System	The technology is fully operational
TRL 9 — Commercial Operation	The final product that has successfully passed final tests and is ready for the mass market

TRL12

Technology Readiness Level
Fundamental Research
Fundamental Research
Lab Testing
Lab Testing
Lab Testing
Real-World Testing
Real-World Testing
Implementation and Production
Implementation and Production

Typical_Reactor13

Typical_Reactor_ID	Typical Reactor Name
BWR	Boiling light water cooled and moderated reactor
FBR	Fast breeder reactor
GCR	Gas cooled, graphite moderated reactor
HTGR	High-temperature Gas-cooled, Graphite-Moderated reactor
HWGCR	Heavy-water-moderated, Gas-cooled reactor
HWLWR	Heavy-water-moderated, Boiling Light-water-cooled reactor
LWGR	Light water cooled, graphite moderated reactor
PHWR	Pressurized heavy water moderated and cooled reactor
PBMR	Pebble Bed Modular Reactor
PWR	Pressurized light water moderated and cooled reactor
SGHWR	Steam-generating Heavy-water reactor

HCFR_CONCEPT_LINEAGE14

Concept_ID	Parent_ID	Generation	Relationship_Type	Developer	Status
HCFR_ROOT_001		0	Origin	USSR	Active
USSR_HCF_001	HCFR_ROOT_001	1	Original Development	USSR	Research
MIT_HCF_001	USSR_HCF_001	2	Adaptation	MIT	Research
LIGHTBRIDGE_HCF_001	USSR_HCF_001	2	Commercial Evolution	Lightbridge	Commercial
CHINA_HCF_001	USSR_HCF_001	2	National Development	China Programs	Research

ORGANIZATIONS15

Org_ID	Organization	Country	Type	Notes
1				

SOURCE_INVENTORY16

Source_ID	Type	Year	Organization	Title	Verification	Notes
1						

Concept_ID	Patent_Count	Publication_Count	Irradiation	PIE	Manufacturing	Licensing	TRL	Confidence
1								

CHANGE_LOG18

Version	Date	Author	Change
v1.1	2026-06-12	EK	Added HCFR_CONCEPT_LINEAGE
v1.1	2026-06-12	EK	Added ORGANIZATIONS
v1.1	2026-06-12	EK	Added SOURCE_INVENTORY
v1.1	2026-06-12	EK	Added EVIDENCE_MATRIX